

Application of Online Arbitration in the World and In Vietnam

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Phuong Hoa Le ⁽²⁾Thi Thu Ha Pham ⁽³⁾Thi Thu Huyen Tran

⁽¹⁾ ⁽²⁾ ⁽³⁾University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Phuong Hoa Le, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

The study summarizes the experience of online arbitration application of developed countries and developing countries similar to Vietnam on the basis of analyzing the characteristics of this type of dispute. Thus, in Vietnam, in the context of rapidly developing e-commerce, leading to increased complaints disputes, online arbitration can be considered as a future for dispute resolution. However, when the belief in online arbitration has not been firmly established, with the current practice in Vietnam, it is recommended to apply online arbitration gradually to prestigious businesses in e-commerce, with simple disputes and prices.

Keywords: Online arbitration, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In conclusion, there have been many topics about online arbitration in the world, there are some topics about online arbitration in Vietnam, but there have not been any studies on online arbitration particularly and the experience of other countries to apply in Vietnam. Referring to the experience of other countries, especially those that have successfully applied online arbitration with condition and, the level similar to Vietnam is extremely necessary because it will help Vietnam save a lot of deploy time and cost. At the same time, the study also answers questions about solutions for the transparency and fairness of e-commerce booming in Vietnam today.

In commercial transactions, especially e-commerce with a high number of transactions, the participants in different countries and especially the transactions in the network environment with the participation of computer systems make disputes related to electronic contracts are increasingly complicated. Online dispute resolution (ODR) in general and online arbitration in particular is dispute resolution mechanism that uses information technology to conduct dispute resolution. Two typical organizations that have used online dispute resolution are auctioning on eBay: SquareTrade.com and domain name disputes organized by international domain name management organization (ICANN).

SquareTrade and ICANN's online dispute resolution process don't require face to face meetings and activities are conducted online. This activity is becoming increasingly necessary for small-value disputes and long-distance transaction parties. Furthermore, online dispute resolution is not only applied to e-commerce transactions, but can also be applied to traditional commercial transactions. For example, SquareTrade has expanded its activities to resolve real estate disputes.

ICANN has developed a standard procedure for resolving disputes related to online domain names so that it can quickly handle disputes related to this activity. With a standard procedure developed by ICANN, dispute resolution organizations such as arbitration and courts can more easily evaluate and resolve related disputes. In addition to ICANN, there are organizations that have developed application programs to assist disputing parties in assessing their rights and obligations in the electronic transaction process. Typically, SmartSettle has developed a model that allows parties to self-assess the extent of violations of rights and obligations in disputes related to e-commerce.

2. International experience of online arbitration in the world

The United States with the Federal Arbitration Act passed - often considered a good support for online arbitration. However, the parties' arbitration agreements still generate tension in jurisprudence and conflict with

state laws. Both the US Federal Trade Commission's approach to e-commerce regulation and the Commonwealth of Australia model of practice require the government to promote dialogue between stakeholders, enforce consumer protection laws, encourage consumer activities and do not impose new legal duties on arbitration suppliers.

Europe, meanwhile, has ensured that the arbitration and conciliation proceedings are as effective, fair and predictable as they are through the rules of the Vienna Rules. Although online arbitration has significant advantages, progress in its actual implementation depends largely on the worldwide digital dissemination.⁵¹ So there is no perfect ODR platform model for Vietnam to refer to in the process of completing the legal basis as well as building technological infrastructure for ODR to be widely applied. There are also other examples as shown below.

2.1. Experience of online arbitration in EU

For online arbitration, according to Karen et al (2002), the most widely proposed penalty relates to "reliability". The escrow developers will draft a set of procedural guidelines for businesses involved in international e-commerce and consumers will have the option of resolving disputes through the use of on-line arbitration. Developers will sanction e-businesses for failing to comply with the arbitration's decision and will lose the ability to lose credibility. The trust operator has a strong incentive to follow the process when the trust operator's reputation is tied to the merchant's reputation, which ensures that the arbitrator's decision is respected. A reliable system developed with standards that can ensure high quality, does not necessarily mean that the lack of trust shows that the enterprise maintains a lower standard. Therefore, this flaw in the reliability system has led some EU member states to establish public bodies to officially approve and monitor trust points in compliance with agreed principles because consumers can't know whether a site is trustworthy or not when they visit it.

There are many countries that refuse to enforce arbitration agreements before disputes in consumer and electronic contracts. In the European Union, according to Paul (2018), e-merchants are allowed to propose dispute resolution via online arbitration but they cannot ask the buyer to do so. The Council of Europe's directives on unfair contractual terms restrict the requirements of online arbitration to deny consumers the right to take advantage of their legal action.

Cybercourt

Cybercourt is a German initiative that provides arbitration for all online disputes arising from online banking, online insurance and other online services. Cybercourt provides an online process using e-mail and Internet Chatboxes. However, the initiators of the arbitration project decided not to offer online arbitration services, because they thought these services were not feasible, at least in Germany because the German Court of Appeals could from refusing to enforce arbitral awards. In addition, a party may cast doubt that in an online arbitration procedure, it is not possible to ascertain that the arbitrator is present at all times. According to the initiators, using technology ensures that referees have been constantly present as videoconferencing can solve the problem but will push Cybercourt's costs too much (Schellekens, 2002). The development of information technology will then gradually solve the above problem and make online arbitration popular in Germany and Europe.

In addition, Directive 2013/11 / EC of the European Parliament and the Council and Amended Regulation (EC) N. 2006/2004 and Directive 2009/22 / EC have ensured that consumers have the right to use online arbitration to resolve their contractual disputes with merchants. Excluding disputes over health and higher education, consumers have the right to use online arbitration for products or services purchased online or offline and merchants established in the Member State or in the other country. Accordingly, dispute resolution agencies that provide online arbitration to consumers are required to ensure binding quality. The competent authorities of the

member states will, after evaluation, notify the European Commission of the list of national dispute settlement bodies (Paul, 2018).

2.2. Experience of online arbitration in Iran

In 1997, based on the Model Law with some adjustments, Iran passed the law on international commercial arbitration called "Law on International Commercial Arbitration" (LICA). LICA needs a signature to make an arbitration award online but does not require a signature to sign an arbitration agreement. Therefore, the validity of electronic signatures and arbitral awards are subject to the laws relating to the acceptance of electronic signatures.

The growing number of internet users and electronic transactions in Iran has helped e-signatures and data messages be recognized by the E-Commerce Law (also known as Electronic Commerce Law (ECL) in 2004. Accordingly, ECL has recognized electronic signatures in place of paper and pen signatures and electronic signatures and electronic documents cannot be denied based on their format in court. Electronic contracts such as "Click wrap contracts" include a link to terms and condition, including an online arbitration agreement that is valid by reference. ECL recognizes all types of digital signatures and Iran has used a hybrid method called a valid digital signature, but not the only acceptable digital signature.

Although Iran has passed ECL laws, the certainty and consistency in those legal systems may not be easily achieved. The law recognizes e-signatures without any condition that it applies to all other non-e-commerce cases such as civil procedure law, contract law, and especially arbitration law. These laws do not explicitly stipulate electronic signatures and documents. Thus electronic signatures can easily be overlooked by judges. To reduce the risk of not accepting electronic signatures in online arbitration agreements, provisions regarding the validity of electronic signatures and electronic documents must be included in the relevant laws, especially arbitration law.

2.3. Experience of online arbitration in US

In the United States and developed countries, dispute resolution online is considered a popular, flexible, convenient mechanism, bringing high efficiency and cost savings. Online arbitration using the website to resolve disputes with the participation of the help of arbitrators with high expertise in traditional dispute resolution and online e-commerce is quite popular. US law allows the creation of organizations that provide online mediation. In the 1980s, the United States developed of three famous online arbitration websites such as cybersettle.com, online resolution.com and smartsettle.com. Websites in the United States that provide online arbitration can be found online, such as OnlineResolution.com or Mediate.com.

With online arbitration decisions in the US, the use of commercial practices can resolve disputes in a fair manner without the use of national law, especially eliminating obstacles of insufficient legal in many countries and facilitate the creation of unified legislation to regulate e-commerce. The arbitration online will gradually develop its own set of precedents and accordingly, the arbitrator can refer to when deciding other cases. For example, for an online domain dispute, ICANN has developed a precedent cited by other ICANN arbitrators and ICANN until it has decided hundreds of new cases based on the precedent system (Karen et al, 2002).

The United States has also adopted "commercial reservations" and US courts have interpreted the term broadly. Low-value consumer transactions will constitute commercial activity under the Convention with the definition of "commercial" meaning any legal relationship with a business purpose. According to research by Philip (2013), provision of online arbitration between citizens of other countries and the United States will be effective if other safeguards against the recognition and enforcement of the Convention provide no use. The reason of refusal foreign arbitral award only if one party is not effectively implemented due to the lack of adequate notice. The US court focused on the overall outcome in determining whether the trial was fair. Accordingly, the arbitral tribunal is widely allowed in the proceeding. In cases where an arbitral award is made by a foreign country on

the grounds that the arbitration proceedings violated a party's procedural rights, the US court will refuse to enforce it (Philip, 2013).

In the United States, Philip (2013) states that if a party to a dispute is reasonably capable of presenting its case and participating in arbitration proceedings, the US court will determine that the procedural rights litigation of the party is not infringed. Accordingly, online arbitration helps all parties involved in small consumer complaints, can present their case by presenting relevant evidence such as receipts, photos, emails, live testimony directly via email or online platforms. Also according to research by Philip (2013), millions of disputes are resolved each year with little or no human interaction. Parties often have no difficulty presenting complaints about small business transactions. As such, any countermeasures against online arbitration will fail under US law (Philip, 2013). Given the extremely limited success of protecting public policy, agreements that provide a fair online arbitration system for low-value commercial transactions will be enforced. Accordingly, any proposed organization that intends to resolve the dispute, ensuring that all agreements between the parties, will grant its jurisdiction over the dispute, is legally valid. At the time of the author's study, 147 countries had adopted the Convention and established from around the world a comprehensive legal framework to determine the validity and enforceability of significant arbitration agreements.

The United States enacted laws that are clearly in effect for electronic agreements, but in many cases of contracting, participating states have refused to comply due to a conflict of laws. In case of dispute, on the grounds that an agreement for arbitration never exists, a party may not accept online arbitration laws of either country.

In the event of a dispute between Internet sites and users (click agreement: through clicking on the box << I accept >> or << I agree >>), the user signs the agreement and commits to use it. Use online arbitration in the event of a dispute. This type of agreement provides maximum speed and convenience for both sellers and consumers, is considered valid and enforceable. In the United States, study of Paul (2018) shows that from the perspective of applicable laws, the above provisions are recognized as enforceable. Even for international B2C disputes, provided that consumers express their consent to use such electronic commerce before signing, they are certainly considered valid and enforced by federal law in the United States.

EBay model - a typical company in the US

According to Karen et al (2002), eBay created a sanction mechanism by informing potential buyers and sellers of the reputation of other eBay members. According to the author's assessment, this model presents information about other members in the same space in which the transaction takes place, so it can outperform the use of reliable information. Both eBay buyers and sellers receive feedback from other members who have entered into transactions with them. Each user has a summary of the results of user feedback. Therefore, the party who wants the transaction can immediately learn the member's profile without having to visit another website. eBay also requires all e-businesses to have a page showing results of an online arbitration process provided to consumers and a page dedicated to comments about them from consumers. Thus, a business with a poor profile will eventually lose consumers. However, the author also leads a recent study showing that most consumers do not check rankings before they buy, so the ranking of the business does not affect the selling price. Users only look at the enterprise's track record after a dispute arises along with the Internet providing a global market for businesses, the impact of the aforementioned model on business activities is not much.

American Arbitration Association (AAA)

AAA, founded in 1926, offers a variety of ADR services, including online arbitration, governed by AAA's rules of procedure for online arbitration and additional procedures. According to research by Schellekens (2002), for each dispute, all case files and submissions are stored on a website that only AAA, the parties and the Arbitrators have access to. If a party wishes to resolve the dispute through arbitration, then that party may submit its request to the AAA Administrative Website. If the complaint is valid and paid, AAA will establish a

profile on the AAA website and notify the address of the Website to the parties. AAA uses the email address provided by the complainant to notify the parties. Accordingly, AAA may decide that arbitration will not be conducted online if one party lacks the ability to participate in online arbitration then the arbitration will be conducted in the traditional way. There will be a hearing if either or both parties request it and can be conducted in person or by phone, videoconference or other means. At testimony, witness testimony may be obtained, cross-checking of witnesses may be conducted and additional documentary evidence may be obtained with the approval of the arbitrator. The arbitrator submits the award on the website and notifies the parties via e-mail of the submission.

2.4. Experience of online arbitration in Singapore

Singapore is one of the leaders in implementing online dispute resolution/arbitration through e @ DR. This is a dispute settlement program conducted by Singapore courts with the support of the Ministry of Justice, the Singapore Arbitration Center, the Singapore International Arbitration Center, the Trade Development Committee and the Economic Development Committee. E @ DR directly solves disputes arising from or related to e-commerce including goods, services, intellectual property rights and domain names. In addition, Singapore has established an international dispute resolution program through an electronic court (Electronic Court Dispute Resolution International - ECDRI) to resolve disputes involving foreign elements. ECDRI operates under the direction of the Singapore court and handles disputes related to intellectual property rights, e-commerce, banking and finance. The trial can be conducted by the Chief Justices of Singapore or the Chief Justices of other countries such as Australia, Europe and the United States and work together through email or webinars.

Online dispute resolution by online arbitration is best suited to conflicts where most of the evidence is online. According to the standards set by the Singapore Court, claims below 20,000 (Singapore dollar) will be considered small. To serve online arbitration, virtual judges and electronic courts have been developed in Singapore. The national eCourt is equipped with new technologies. Accordingly, the parties to the dispute no longer need to go to court. Instead, they can participate in court proceedings through technology.

2.5. Experience of online arbitration in Indonesia

Experience of Indonesia related to the application of online arbitration related to legal practice. Indonesian law requires arbitration to be performed in writing. This is met by an online arbitration referred to in Article 4 of Law No. 30 of 1999 providing that if an agreement is made to resolve a dispute by correspondence, telex, telegram, fax, e- Letters, or any other form of contact, must be attached to the receipt of the parties. This provision allows e-mail to be considered as an arbitration agreement. Another requirement is the signature of the parties to the dispute in the arbitration agreement. The use of electronic signatures in an arbitration agreement in force since Article 11 of Law No. 11 of 2008 related to Information and Electronic Transactions stipulates that electronic signature will be legally effective. It is legal and legally effective to meet certain requirements, thus, according to above regulation, digital signatures are equal to manual signatures and legally valid. Indonesian laws clearly state that an online arbitration agreement is an agreement made by the disputing parties through technological means to resolve their disputes. The online route is the legal basis for conducting an online arbitration hearing and can be done in full by the use of electronic means, such as each arbitration participant sitting in front of audio and video camera equipment and able to communicate with each other.

Even if the arbitration position has not been determined by the parties to the dispute, Article 31 of Law No. 30 of 1999 provides that if the parties have chosen an arbitration procedure, they must agree on the rules for time frame and place of the arbitrator and if the time frame and venue are not determined, the arbitrator or arbitral tribunal shall identify them.

As such, no provision of Law No. 30 of 1999 prohibits online legal proceedings and trials as long as they are conducted on the principles of transparency, equality and due process. However, arbitrators do not have the

authority to enforce and recognize the online arbitration awards they have made but by national courts enforcing their laws governing that process.

Law No. 30 of 1999 divides arbitral awards into two categories, that is, domestic (international and national arbitration awards (foreign arbitral awards. Arbitration awards are types of domestic strategy) national jurisdiction if the proceeding and arbitration body is under Indonesian jurisdiction Article 1 (9 of Law No. 30 of 1999 de nes international (foreign arbitral awards as an award awarded by an organization) arbitration or personal arbitration outside the jurisdiction of the Republic of Indonesia, or a decision of an arbitration organization or individual arbitration, as required by Indonesian law, is considered an international arbitral award, The question is how to classify arbitration online when all arbitration processes t The arbitration is conducted online.the nationality of the arbitration, so the nationality of the arbitration online also depends on the arbitration seat written in the awards.

In Indonesia, according to Article 59 of Law No. 30 of 1999 regarding the enforcement of domestic arbitration awards online, within 30 (thirty days from the date the award was given, the original text or an authentic copy of The arbitral award must be handed over to the District Court Clerk or the arbitration award cannot be made, so in Indonesia, an online arbitration award must be printed and signed by the arbitrators. It is clear that all arbitration stages can be conducted online in Indonesia, but the final stage is to enforce the arbitration award to print and sign the arbitration award online.

In summary, the enforceability of online arbitral awards is huge because online arbitral awards can be printed and signed by arbitrators (possibly by electronic signature). As such, online arbitration in Indonesia may be used for business purposes because the relevant Indonesian law is quite adequate and supports the use of this type of arbitration.

3. Online arbitration in Vietnam

3.1. Legal provisions on online dispute resolution and online arbitration

Since 2005, Vietnam has applied the New York Convention 1958 related to arbitration and two global reference documents on e-commerce, the Model Law on Electronic Commerce in 1996 (amended in 1998) and the Model Law on Electronic Signatures (2001) issued by the United Nations International Trade Law Commission (UNCITRAL).⁵⁸ On that basis, the Law on Electronic Transactions 2005 and the Law on Information Technology 2006 were enacted to help recognize electronic transactions and thereby promote the development of electronic commerce.

Based on the aforementioned laws, Decree 57/2006 / ND-CP and Circular No. 09/2008 / TT-BCT of the Government on e-commerce are also issued to regulate the provision of information and contracting on e-commerce websites for traders use e-commerce websites to sell goods or provide services, customers and organizations and individuals own e-commerce websites. This Decree has introduced a mechanism to review and confirm the content of the contract. Accordingly, customers can review, supplement, modify and confirm the content of the transaction before using the online ordering function to submit an offer to sign a contract. At the same time, this mechanism also allows customers to review information provided by traders through the website, to choose to cancel transactions or confirm the offer to sign contracts.

Decree No. 26/2007 / ND-CP detailing the implementation of the Law on Electronic Transactions on Digital Signature, Digital Signature Authentication Service and the management, provision and use of digital signature authentication services. Accordingly, the law recognizes the legal value of digital signatures, a data message is considered to be met if the data message is signed with digital signatures. At the same time, foreign digital signatures and certificates are recognized and have the same validity and validity as Vietnam's digital signatures and digital certificates. Regarding the issue of resolving disputes and complaints between the parties in the provision and use of digital signature authentication services to the public, Decree 26/2007 / ND-CP stipulates

in general that settlement is done on the basis of a contract between the parties and provisions on complaints, denunciations and relevant provisions of law.

Circular No. 09/2008 / TT-BCT regulated the guidance of e-commerce decree on information provision and conclusion of contracts on e-commerce websites. Accordingly, the law stipulates that the contract concluded from the interaction between customers and the online ordering function on e-commerce websites must not be denied legal validity just because there is no inspection or intervention directly by the trader at every step of the contracting process. At the same time, the E-commerce website must provide customers with information on the terms of the contract before the time the customer submits the offer to sign the contract. Traders must provide buyers with sufficient information, including information on goods and services; price information; Information about transaction terms; Information about shipping on forwarder and payment method. In case of disputes related to contracts entered into on an e-commerce website, the settlement of disputes must be based on the terms of the contract published at the website at the time of signing the contract and the relevant laws and traders must not take advantage of their advantages in the electronic environment to unilaterally resolve disputes without the consent of customers. As such, traders must publish on the website a specific mechanism and process for resolving customer complaints related to contracts entered into on the website.

Decree No. 52 / ND-CP / 2013 dated May 16, 2013 was issued to regulate e-commerce relations and regulations on the development, application and management of e-commerce activities. This Decree contains many important provisions which provide specific guidance on the signing and implementation of e-commerce contracts. Accordingly, the Decree prescribes the conditions for electronic documents in commercial transactions to be legally valid as the originals, criteria for evaluating integrity and ensuring reliability. The Decree also deals with contracts of traders, organizations and individuals selling goods. Accordingly, if an e-commerce website with an online ordering function applies to each specific goods or service introduced on that website, the introductory information about the goods, services, and articles Relevant amounts shall be regarded as notices of invitation to sign contracts. At the same time, e-documents generated and sent by customers using the online ordering function are considered as customers' contractual offers for goods or services.

This Decree also has important provisions related to dispute resolution in e-commerce. Accordingly, Traders, organizations and individuals that own sales e-commerce websites shall receive and handle customer complaints related to contracts entered into on their e-commerce websites. When a dispute arises during contract performance, the parties must resolve it on the basis of the terms of the contract published on the website at the time of signing the contract and the provisions of relevant laws. In order to ensure fairness and protect consumers, the law also stipulates that traders, organizations and individuals selling goods and providing services cannot take advantage of their advantages in the electronic environment to unilaterally resolving disputes without the customers' consent. The law also generally stipulates that dispute resolution must be through negotiation between parties, mediation, arbitration or a court in accordance with the applicable dispute resolution procedures. Thus, the provisions on resolving E-commerce disputes have just stopped at the general principles of resolving disputes to handle violations in e-commerce without specific provisions on specific mechanisms to advance ODR operation. The new law only requires traders and organizations providing e-commerce services to publish clearly on the website the process of receiving, responsibilities to handle customers' complaints and the dispute settlement mechanism related to contracts entered into its ecommerce website and participate in mediating disputes arising between customers and sellers on its e-commerce website.

Another important circular related to e-commerce in general and e-commerce disputes in particular is Circular No. 10/2008 / TT-BTTTT, that regulates the settlement of disputes over Vietnam national domain names ".

Accordingly, the law provides for the resolution of domain name disputes, which are implemented through the forms of the parties' choice, including: Through negotiation, conciliation; via arbitration and suing in court. In case of resolving domain name disputes through negotiation and conciliation, the parties may perform conciliation before or during the proceeding process with the participation of the relevant ".vn" domain name

registrar or VNNIC to handle disputed domain names. In case the parties choose to resolve domain name disputes through arbitration, the procedure for resolving domain name disputes arising from commercial activities at arbitration centers shall comply with the provisions of law. Thus, the law refers to the form of handling disputes through arbitration but not to mention that the form of handling is online or offline even with the typical case of e-commerce as domain name disputes.

Circular No. 46/2010 / TT-BTC regulated the state management of the operation of e-commerce websites established by traders and organizations in the territory of Vietnam to sell goods or provide services. In particular, the law requires traders to formulate and promulgate regulations on management of e-commerce trading floors, including: principles, transaction processes, assurance of transaction safety, protection of human rights of consumer, limiting liability in the case of arising technical errors of the trading floor. At the same time, the e-commerce floor must publicize the mechanism for resolving disputes arising in the course of trading on the electronic commerce trading floor. When a dispute arises, the organization operating the e-commerce platform must provide consumers with seller registration information, actively support consumers in protecting their legitimate rights and interests. Based on the above-mentioned discussions, Vietnam has not mentioned or mentioned it is very sketchy to the reality in online arbitration in resolving disputes even with electronic transactions. Due to the transnational nature of e-commerce transactions and the arising disputes to effectively regulate e-commerce and online activities in Vietnam, a synchronized legal framework is required in accordance with international law and practice.

The Commercial Arbitration Law 2010 in Article 16 also clearly stipulates the form of arbitration agreement. Accordingly, in addition to the form of written information exchange agreement between the parties; through a lawyer, notary public or competent organization; reference to a document expressing an arbitration agreement, the agreement may also be established through exchanges between the parties by telegram, fax, telex, email and other forms as prescribed by law. This provision is also clarified in Article 7 of this Resolution guiding the implementation of a number of provisions of the Commercial Law Law 2014. Accordingly, in case the arbitration agreement has unclear content, it can be understood in many other meanings. Each of them shall apply the provisions of the Civil Code to explain. At the same time, obligations arising from transactions or contracts where the parties have established a legal arbitration agreement in such transaction or arbitration agreement will still apply to the parties. be transferred and the transferee, unless otherwise agreed by the parties. On this basis, Vietnam's VIAC also stipulates the establishment of an arbitration agreement through videoconferencing and other similar forms with hard document.

Most notably, the government recently issued Decree 22/2017 on trade mediation. This Decree prescribes the scope, principles, order and procedures for settling disputes by commercial conciliators, trade mediators, trade mediation organizations or foreign trade mediation organizations in Vietnam and state management of commercial mediation activities. The disputing parties may reconcile by themselves or request other agencies, organizations or individuals to mediate according to the agreement of the parties in accordance with law.

When conducting mediation, the parties have the right to choose the Mediation Rules of a commercial mediation organization to conduct mediation or to negotiate the mediation order and procedures themselves. If the parties do not agree on the order and procedures for conciliation, the commercial conciliator shall conduct mediation according to the order and procedures that the commercial conciliator considers suitable to the circumstances of the case and the wishes of the mediator parties and their consent. During the mediation process, commercial mediators have the right to make proposals to resolve disputes. In addition, the location and time of mediation shall be agreed upon by the parties or by the choice of a commercial mediator in cases where the parties have no agreement. Thus, although not clearly stated, but many professional mediation organizations have implemented mediation and arbitration in the form of online, these organizations can fully propose implementation or implementation under authorization.

3.2. The application of online arbitration in Vietnam

The application of online arbitration

According to statistics, the number of disputes resolved by arbitration in Vietnam accounts for less than 1% of the total number of commercial disputes that are accepted and adjudicated by the court every year.

Vietnam has a target that the proportion of disputes resolved by trade centers must account for less than 10% of the total number of accepted disputes, while the domestic dispute currently accounts for about 70% and tends to increase, especially in FDI enterprises, the demand for dealing with serious disputes is not small.

In the era of technology 4.0, electronic transactions are increasingly popular, demonstrating that electronic evidence is increasingly used by parties to commercial transactions through apps: wechat, viber, email. Data from the Vietnam Association of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) also shows that up to 50% of these businesses have applied digital technologies to their transactions and up to 74% conduct combined transactions by online method between the parties. Businesses in Vietnam consider themselves to be weak but if using online arbitration, whether the business is the plaintiff or the defendant can win the case ... The reason all depends on the evidence of transactions and arguments are provided. Typically, disputes involve import-export enterprises, Vietnamese enterprises are often injured or sued, accounting for 60% and due to geographical difficulties, the most important form of online processing is often used.

Contract dispute resolution in e-commerce in Vietnam is now implemented according to the traditional trade dispute settlement mechanism, in the form of negotiation, conciliation, arbitration and court. These methods require the parties to meet to resolve a dispute. However, with characteristics different from traditional commercial contracts such as the process of signing and implementing e-commerce contracts performed on the Internet environment, entities are far away from each other, the number of transactions If they are implemented at a high speed and fast, etc., the actual application of commercial dispute settlement measures has caused inconvenience, costly time and effort of the parties to the dispute. Therefore, many cases of dispute occur but due to the fear of complicated dispute resolution mechanism, which takes a lot of time and effort, the parties have to "pity" for it.

In Vietnam, through author's survey of a number of disputes on e-commerce sites⁶⁴, it is a fact that online service providers or sellers of online goods and services establishing arbitration rules online but lacking supervision, transparency, objectivity, fairness of the government. The above-mentioned arbitration providers are also not penalized for causing damage to customers unless they complain to the Competition Administration Department, therefore, often put adverse conditions for customers. Parties to commercial contracts do not have faith and organizations stand out to arbitrate, especially online arbitration because there is no face-to-face meeting. The popular method of dispute is still the court for large-scale commercial disputes and between businesses. Online arbitration has been applied at an early stage and mostly between businesses and consumers.

For example, one of the largest e-commerce websites in Vietnam, Tiki has initially been an intermediary (internal arbitration and no legality) between customers and traders on its website. Tiki is always responsible for receiving and handling customer complaints and promoting solutions for negotiation and mediation between the parties. The processes of complaint follow these steps:

- o Step 1: Customers complain about goods and services of Sellers buying on e-commerce platform tiki.vn done by phone, email.
- o Step 2: Tiki Care will receive complaints, contact clarifying the Customer's requirements as soon as possible and no later than 05 working days from the date of receiving the request.
- o Step 3: Tiki can ask the Customer and / or the Seller to provide information and evidence related to the transaction, the product is completely online to verify, clarify the case and take appropriate action.

o Step 4: In the event that Tiki has tried to resolve complaints and disputes but the incident is beyond the capabilities and authority of Tiki, Tiki will ask the Customer to take the case to the competent State agency to resolve according to provisions of law.

Accordingly, the parties including sellers and buyers have an important and responsible role in actively resolving the matter. The Seller is responsible for providing documents, documents, papers, and other evidence to prove and clarify information related to the incident that is causing the customer's conflict.

Tiki also states that any dispute arising out of or relating to transactions on the Website or the above Terms and Conditions will be settled by means of negotiation, conciliation, arbitration and / or Court under the Law on consumer rights protection in 2010, in Chapter 4 on Settlement of disputes between consumers and organizations and individuals trading goods and services.

Application of online arbitration at Arbitration Centers in Vietnam

Pacific International Commercial Arbitration Center (PIAC)

Pacific International Commercial Arbitration Center (PIAC) was established in 2006 and currently has nearly 80 arbitrators, meeting the needs of the business community for a reliable dispute resolution institution, efficient, fair and independent in Vietnam.

PIAC is considered as a non-profit organization with the goal of promoting optional dispute resolution activities (ADR) and strengthening cooperation between experts and practices to resolve commerce disputes.

The mediation/arbitration process begins when PIAC receives a notice of mediation/arbitration acceptance and advances the mediation fee of the party who receives the mediation request. Any acceptance of mediation/mediation/arbitration must be made in writing or in forms of equivalent value in writing including telegraph, data message, telex, fax and other forms as prescribed by law. PIAC may also accept a part of the process of online arbitration. In accordance with Article 3 of the Rules of Procedure, Notices, Documents sent by the Center to the parties at the address provided by the parties and may be delivered by direct delivery, registered mail, electronic mail, fax or any other form any other method that acknowledges this submission. The arbitral tribunal may hold meetings in a manner and wherever appropriate.

Vietnam International Arbitration Center (VIAC)

With over 25 years of operation, VIAC has resolved thousands of disputes by means of commercial arbitration related to a variety of trade fields such as goods trading, insurance, transportation, finance, banking, investment, construction... VIAC's arbitration award is not only implemented smoothly in Vietnam but also recognized and enforced in 159 countries and territories. VIAC has constantly grown, developed and became a cornerstone of the justice community of domestic and foreign businesses.

In 2019, VIAC resolved more than 200 domestic disputes, more than 25 disputes involving foreign elements, including the most in China, Singapore and South Korea. In particular, the field of dispute using the most arbitration is buying and selling goods and real estate with the total value of dispute is over 6600 billion VND. However, this organization did not specify the proportion of disputes made online, showing that this form is still applied very limited at the largest arbitration center in Vietnam.⁶⁹ VIAC believes that in fact, e-hearing has been used in arbitration proceedings from the past few years. A trial is conducted entirely by electronic devices, using various digital technologies, to eliminate the need for hard copy documents. Typically, the courtroom is set up with computer screens to display electronic documents, using a common database. VIAC also used video conferencing to submit evidence.

The Civil Procedure Code does not currently have specific regulations on the order, procedures and competence to settle disputes for e-commerce. Cases of settling disputes and complaints are inconsistent with each case in localities. In addition, because disputes in online transactions are related to many different fields, businesses

when disputes occur often send letters to the wrong agency because the law has not specified causing waste of time for handling cases when transferring to other managing units. In Vietnam, there is a great gap between development practices and the legal framework in this area. Accordingly, while e-commerce disputes are increasing, Vietnam has had laws on e-commerce but almost no mention of regulations related to ODR method.

Southern Commercial Arbitration Center (STAC)

The Southern Commercial Arbitration Center was established in 2017 with nearly 30 highly qualified arbitrators. The center has strengths in resolving disputes arising in the field of finance and bank credit, which are trusted and selected by many banks. The center is a non-governmental organization, has the legal status, its own seal and account, and operates autonomously financially in accordance with the law of Vietnam. In addition to banking and finance, the Center also handles disputes between parties arising from commercial activities; disputes arising between parties in which at least one party has commercial activities; other disputes between the parties that are required by law to be settled by arbitration. The information on this center's website shows that this center has no experience handling online arbitration. However, pursuant to Article 3, this Center's Rules of Procedure may also accept a part of the process of online arbitration similar to the STAC mentioned above.

3.3. Opportunities of applying online arbitration in Vietnam Regarding the development of E-commerce

E-commerce is increasingly showing its role as a pioneer of the digital economy in creating new production and consumption values, and a driving force for development in the coming time.

According to Emarketer.com, since 2017, there have been about 120 million e-commerce transactions carried out every day, but of which 2-5% of transactions arising a single dispute as of 2017 were about 942.8 million from 2017. With such a large number of disputes, traditional methods of resolving disputes directly in court are not feasible and very expensive. Therefore the use of online arbitration is required.

In Vietnam, according to data from Vietnam E-Commerce White Paper 2019, the size of Vietnam's retail e-commerce market - B2C in 2018 increased by 30% compared to 2017, estimated to reach USD 8.06 billion accounting for about 4.2% of the total retail sales of goods and service revenue nationwide. The growth of Vietnam's e-commerce in 2016 and 2017 were 23% and 24%, respectively.

According to the report "Southeast Asia Internet Economy 2018" by Google - Temasek and published, Vietnam will become the country with the fastest growing e-commerce in the region with the growth of e-commerce in the period. 2015 - 2025 about 43%. Specifically, the number of people participating in online shopping in 2018 was 39.9 million people with an online shopping value of one person estimated to reach 202 USD. The percentage of Internet users participating in online shopping at least once a year has increased slightly from 67% in 2017 to 70% in 2018. The percentage of online shoppers looking for information online is up to 86%. In particular, the rate of online orders via mobile devices continued to grow, reaching 81%, showing that the trend of shopping via mobile devices is growing significantly.

Also according to the above survey, "Poor quality products compared to advertising" is still the biggest obstacle when shopping online accounting for 83% of consumers' choice to participate in the survey. So for these cases, the method required to use will have to be an online arbitration based on agreement before purchase.

About information technology infrastructure

In recent years, ICT infrastructure in Vietnam such as computers, telecommunication network equipment, telecommunication services and internet has been increasingly invested and developed. Vietnam has become one of the leading ICT infrastructure countries in the region, the monthly price of mobile or Internet services compared to developing countries is the lowest in the region, which is a significant advantage.⁷⁵ Network providers have successfully deployed IPv6 and 4G services and initially mastered 5G technology to help

accelerate the rapidly growing demand of network services and e-commerce in general, online transactions in particular.

According to the E-commerce Index Report (2019), in 2018, Vietnam's e-commerce continues to develop comprehensively with a growth rate of over 30% and will reach the goal of USD 10 billion for businesses in the E-commerce Development Master Plan for the period of 2016 - 2020. In addition, most businesses primarily use computers and laptops, the percentage of enterprises using digital signatures and translations. Digital signature authentication has increased by more than 30% compared to previous years.

About the legal basis framework

Vietnam has applied the New York Convention 1958, the Model Law on Electronic Commerce in 1996 and the Model Law on Electronic Signatures (2001). Although compared to developed countries, the level of recognition of such international laws is still low, but it has also facilitated the enactment of laws that facilitate the development of electronic commerce.

The legal system on e-commerce in Vietnam is an initial basis to promote the development of online arbitration with more than 14 laws and 18 bylaws in the direction of clarifying e-commerce activities, entities involved in e-commerce activities, while strengthening the management role of state agencies.⁷⁷ Therefore, the above platforms are the basis for elaborating specific laws on online arbitration in the future. The law of Vietnam has acknowledged the legal value of electronic data messages, then the submission of documents and evidence via electronic means to perform online arbitration will have a basis for implementation. In addition, the provisions on resolving e-commerce disputes are basically prescribed in Decree No. 52/2013 / ND-CP on e-commerce. Finally, in order to provide regulations on resolving disputes for all types of consumers, including goods and services online, the Law on Consumer Protection 2014 also clearly stipulates the order and procedures for settling disputes between consumers and organizations and individuals trading goods and / or services including arbitration.

About the capacity of Vietnamese businesses

Vietnamese businesses increasingly participate in e-commerce activities with a variety of forms such as sales e-commerce websites, e-commerce service websites, online auction websites but compliance with regulations. The regulations of enterprises are not high. As a result, disputes related to e-commerce, most notably about the content of electronic contracts, are increasing and mostly are small value transactions and from contract content such as slow delivery, late payments according to the agreement. In addition, the management and processing of electronic data of Vietnamese enterprises is still limited, the confidentiality of electronic data is not focused, leading to unsafety. The above content is a significant cause of online disputes arising, from which the online arbitration mechanism has the opportunity to be applied and poses urgent requirements to be performed on the basis of handling. Poor dispute is a barrier in the process of popularizing and developing e-commerce in Vietnam.

The overload of the court system

Thousands of cases related to commercial disputes are waiting in line to be tried at courts of all levels but have not been able to handle them because they are overloaded and not enough judges to handle definitive decision. The Government of Vietnam has also strongly addressed this issue, requiring shortening of the time to resolve disputes in court from 400 days to 300 days. But in fact, most of the economic cases in Vietnam are never less than 400 days. On average, the fastest time in court is 1-2 years, on average, 3-4 years, many cases up to 5-6 years. Including cases involving foreign elements brought to court, tried many times but could not resolve.⁷⁸ This fact opens up a great opportunity for online arbitration that is not dependent on the infrastructure of the court and arbitration experts can handle the dispute anywhere and anytime via Internet and IT systems.

In addition, Vietnam has a young population and access to information technology, a high rate of Internet users are important conditions to promote the use of online arbitration in goods purchase and sale transactions. Through e-commerce and step by step increasing consumer confidence with e-commerce and consumers' rights are increasingly better protected when participating in electronic transactions.

4. Conclusion

In order to meet practical requirements, the socio-economic conditions and laws must be mobilized and transformed, so the stagnation in the psychological sentiment of Vietnamese people who love stability will not be able to meet them. The Vietnamese do not have the habit of obeying the law and the concept of law, do not consider the law as a means to protect themselves, argue that the law is to dominate rather than a tool to regulate society and protect people especially when they are familiar with the law.

Vietnamese people are often afraid to take part in disputes, often less concerned about the responsibility of the business, so when there is a problem of product dissatisfaction, Vietnamese people often make complaints, especially especially with disputes of small value. In addition, psychologists want to directly participate in resolving disputes because they do not trust the parties will comply with the law or ensure honesty in the online environment while during offline disputes, the parties may consider other's attitude, as well as using body language.

The unwillingness of businesses

Although there have been pressing demands when e-commerce has grown exponentially over the years, the number of businesses that are truly eligible to apply the online arbitration mechanism to their operations remains too little. The Vietnamese government and businesses have not really paid attention and invested in ODR, although some private companies have initially implemented services that allow consumers to settle complaints and complaints online via the website.

In addition to limited technical infrastructure investment, the enterprise also lacks a team of trained technicians in support of online arbitration activities. Therefore, the business itself has not created the trust of customers when it has not dared to stand out and resolve disputes in a public and transparent manner to customers.

The ambiguity of the legal framework

Vietnam still enforces the internalization of international conventions by ratifying and then enacting national laws but the laws are often developed in long period and there are many points that would be inappropriate with international practices while e-commerce is on a global level.

It is possible that the online arbitration model is known by businesses that want to be applied, consumers know, but there is no direct regulation of law that prevents the parties from applying, or the dispute solvers themselves. It will also feel awkward to use it. ODR provider's liability rules in the event of a breach of service agreement are not specific. In addition to the absence of legal documents governing ODR activities, the relevant laws only stipulate very general methods, so to apply online arbitration, a combination of laws is required and this will increase the subjectivity of the arbitration institution and make it difficult to apply.

One problem related to the fear of using online arbitration in e-commerce is the number of e-commerce websites in Vietnam providing sufficient and up-to-date information in Vietnamese and English, which are not the majority in Vietnam. This situation leads to difficulties for partners who do not use Vietnamese language. On the contrary, many websites in the world are only in English and their native languages, while the popularity of English in Vietnam is not high, thus it will prevent Vietnamese consumers from using online arbitration services that provided. Language barriers make it impossible for customers and partners to understand the provisions of the dispute provided on the website and cannot take risks to conduct transactions.

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